

CONCRETE FOR LOWER KIHANSI DAM

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents detailed information on concrete used in the construction of Lower Kihansi Dam. The paper outlines the procedure used in concrete production, aggregate production, cement selection, concrete mix design and measures taken to avoid thermal cracks in massive dam concrete.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Kihansi dam is 50,000 m³ concrete and 25 metres high gravity dam which creates a line reservoir of approximately 1,000,000 cubic metres' storage capacity corresponding to an energy of 300 Megawatts which will be installed in two phases. The first phase installed three units which produce 180 Megawatts, and the

second phase will install two units which will produce 120 megawatts. The underground power station is located on the Kihansi river at the Udzungwa escarpment. The dam is located in U-shaped valley within a unit of biotitic gneiss. The dam was constructed from 1996 and was commissioned in March 2000.

The concrete used for the construction of Kihansi dam was divided into two categories, namely massive concrete and structural concrete. As per technical specifications, the structural concrete was defined as concrete with construction thickness of less than 2 metres, above this dimension, the concrete was classified as massive. The concrete grade used for the construction of the dam is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The concrete cube compressive strength requirements of Kihansi Dam

Concrete class	Max. Agg. size	Age of testing	slump (mm)	Remarks
C25	25	28	70±20	Structural/Massive
C25	64	28	70± 20	Structural/Massive
C30	64	90	30±20	Massive concrete
C25	90	90	30±20	Massive concrete

Concrete grade 25/25 [*designated Mix 2 C25/25*] was used in all intake structures, the downstream side of the overflow section of the dam and at spillways. Concrete grade 25/64 [*designated Mix 2 C25/64*] was used in locations where the concrete was in direct contact with rock/soil or in unreinforced locations. Concrete grade 30/64 [*designated Mix 4*] was a massive dam concrete which was used in the outer part of the dam [*surface*]. Concrete grade 25/90 [*designated Mix 5*] was massive dam concrete which was used in the inner part of the dam [*core*]. The project specification called for Mix 2 and Mix 4 to be impermeable.

The dam was divided into 15 blocks in the form of transversal joints. The specified depth of one lift was 2.5 metres. The lift thickness of 2.5 metres was selected to reduce the number of construction joints which are likely to be a source of structural weakness and seepage through the dam as the planes of weakness are likely to be created between two successive concrete lifts.

2.0 AGGREGATES

The project specifications favoured the use of natural aggregates for concrete production. They were several nearby sources of natural sand which were

investigated as potential sources of sand for concrete production. It was found that all investigated sand sources were either excessively contaminated with mica or were not economically viable to exploit. Therefore, the use of crushed coarse aggregates and crushed fine aggregates was found to be the only viable solution for concrete production for dam and powerhouse construction.

About 80% of aggregates for concrete production were obtained after crushing biotitic gneiss rock which was hauled from the underground excavation of tunnels in Kihansi and transported to the dam site using dump trucks. 15% of the aggregate was obtained after crushing rock hauled from a quarry located about 12 km north of the dam site. The remaining 5% were obtained after crushing the rock coming from shaft excavation at the dam site area.

2.1 Aggregates Quarries and Crushing Plants

Two crushing plants were installed in the project area specifically for crushing aggregates for the construction of the dam, tunnels, vertical shaft and powerhouse. Crushers were processing the aggregates to the grain sizes of 0/6, 6/12, 12/25, 25/64, and 64/90 mm. The first crushing plant was installed in Kihansi, 16 km from the dam site while the second crusher plant was installed at the dam site area. Typical gradings of aggregates produced for dam construction are shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Aggregates characteristics

All aggregates for concrete production were obtained after crushing rock from the Udzungwa scarp. The rock in this area is characterised by high mica content. The most predominant rock within the scarp is biotite gneiss, although some tested rock samples showed a granitic composition. The main minerals present in the rock are quartz, feldspar and biotite, which in most cases was found to be the main constituents.

Figure 1: The gradings of aggregates used for production Kihansi Dam concrete

2.3 The Effect of Mica in the Sand

The presence of mica in the sand affected the concrete characteristics by reducing the compressive strength and increasing the water demand. Based on the analysis of concrete mix design trials conducted on-site, it was found that the presence of mica in natural and crushed sand available within the project vicinity reduced the resultant cube compressive strength in the range of 8-23%. The water demand was found to increase in the range of 8-16% [2]. Therefore, additional cement content was required to compensate for the poor aggregate quality available within the project vicinity.

2.4 Aggregates' shape

The biotitic gneiss rock available within the project vicinity is highly foliated. Shape and the grading of the crushed aggregates used for concrete production were affected by the platy-like-structure of the mica particles and the rock foliation. The mica particles have a visible cleavage plane making the produced aggregates to be flaky and elongated irrespective of crusher settings. The presence of mica within the rock affected the grading since mica was the weakest mineral within the rock; therefore, the crushed sand produced contained an excessive amount of mica. During the crushing process, the mica particles crushed down to dust. The

geotechnical and chemical properties of the aggregates available within the project vicinity are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of geotechnical and chemical properties of aggregates

Test	Results	Specification
Sodium sulphate Soundness	1.9%	10% Maximum
Sulphate	0.015%	0.25% maximum
Particle density	2.685	
Water Absorption	0.25-0.31%	
Aggregate crushing value [ACV]	25-35%	35% Maximum
Ten per cent fine [TPF]	90-140 KN	
Organic impurities	Negligible	
Alkali silica reaction [ASR]	Not reactive	
Flakiness index [FI]	16-25%	20% Maximum
Clay lumps	0.58%	2% maximum
Los Angeles abrasion value [LAAI]	42%	
Mineralogical analysis		
Quartz	20-80%	
Feldspar	15-55	
Biotite	25-60	
Muscovite	Trace to 8%	

3.0 CEMENT SELECTION

The project specifications called for a low heat cement with the heat of hydration of less than 290kJ/g at seven days as measured using the heat of hydration of hydraulic cement [*heat of solution method*] as per ASTM C186. This requirement of limiting the heat of the cement hydration was specified to minimise the possibility of having cracks caused by thermal stress within the concrete.

Cement brands available locally were tested, but none of them was found suitable for dam construction. The most feasible solution was to use imported Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag [GGBS] which was site blended in the ratio of 1:1 with Portland cement CEM II 32.5R sourced locally.

3.1 OPC and OPC/ GGBS blend

After blending OPC and GGBS, the characteristics of the resultant cement blend like setting time, bleeding, the heat of hydration, fineness and compressive strength were modified. The summary of the test results is shown in Table 4, from which it can be seen that the initial and final setting time was extended. Due to extensions of setting time, the bleeding increased [*Figure 2*]. The 2,7 and 28 days cube compressive strength were lower than that of OPC, but the cube compressive strength of blended cement was higher than that of OPC at 90 and 180 days [*Figure 3*] while the heat of hydration was lowered as shown by test results in Table 3.

Table 3: The total heat under the adiabatic condition for OPC and a blend of OPC/GGBS

Age in days	OPC	OPC/GGBS (1:1)
1	200	120
3	240	210
5	250	240
7	260	245

Table 4: Comparison between OPC and GGBS/OPC blend

Characteristics	Control OPC	50%:50% OPC:GGBS
Particle density	3.02	2.93
Initial setting time (minutes)	130	190
Final setting time (minutes)	190	240
Fineness (cm ² /g)	3145	3450
Standard consistency (%)	25.4	27.4
Le Chatelier Expansion (mm)	0	1
2 days Compressive strength (Mpa)	17.0	7.6
7 days compressive strength (Mpa)	28.0	21.1
28 days compressive strength (Mpa)	42.0	39.1

Figure 2: Bleeding of OPC and OPC/GGBS blend for Mix 5

Figure 3: Strength development curve for OPC and blend of OPC: GGBS [water-binder ratio of 0.60]

4.0 CONCRETE MIX DESIGN

The concrete mix design involved extensive laboratory testing of aggregates, cement, mineral additives like silica fume, fly ash, ground granulated blast furnace slag [GGBS] and admixtures like water reducer and retarders. The concrete mix design aimed at achieving mixes meeting the project specified requirements like strength, durability, permeability and resistance to cracking. Therefore, the intent was to design mixes with a low amount of cement to reduce the formation of thermal stresses within the massive dam concrete. The ingredients for the mixes used for the construction of the dam as developed during the concrete mix design is shown in Table 5.

Figure 4: Grading for massive dam concrete (Mix 4 and 5)

Table 5: Concrete mixes used for Kihansi Dam

Component	Mix 2° C25/25	Mix 2° C25/25	Mix 2° C25/64	Mix 4 C30/64	Mix 5 C25/90
OPC	190	160	165	132.5	105
Slag	190	160	165	132.5	105
Silica fume	0	20	0	0	0
Crushed sand	725	700	495	530	535
Coarse aggregate	1135	1140	1415	1500	1635
Water	215	215	180	155	140
Water binder ratio	0.57	0.58	0.55	0.58	0.67
Plasticizer	1.6	1.4	1.3	1.1	0.8
Slump	70±20	70±20	70±20	30±20	30±20
Permeability	<1.0cm	<1.0cm	<1.0cm	1.0 cm	-----
Temperature (fresh concrete.)	20°C	20°C	20°C	20°C	20°C
Max. Curing temp.	54°C	48 °C	48 °C	43 °C	38 °C
7 days strength (MPa)	18.8	17.8	16.3	16.5	12.6
28 days strength (MPa)	30.0	31.0	29.5	26.6	22.3
90 days strength (MPa)	34.1	33.1	34.9	32.2	27.6
Tensile strength (MPa)	3.5	3.4	3.5	3.2	2.5

The water binder ratio for concrete was defined as $\frac{w}{2k + s + c}$ whereas 'w' is water content,

'k' is silica fume, 's' is GGBS and 'c' is cement content. Based on the definition of "water binder ratio", the efficiency of silica fume was set to two while the efficiency of GGBS was set to one.

5.0 HEAT GENERATION AND THERMAL TREATMENT MEASURES

Crack resistance for the massive dam concrete was considered as the most critical requirement. Therefore, the heat of hydration of concrete was considered as a crucial concrete design issue. The maximum cement content and maximum heat of hydration were specified. The maximum temperature of the fresh concrete of 27°C and the maximum curing temperature of 65°C was specified to limit the adverse effects of thermal stresses within the massive dam concrete.

In most cases, the concrete class C25 and C30 pose no problem during mix design and production. However, with poor quality aggregate available within the project vicinity, led to concrete to be proportioned with high cement content to compensate for the poor aggregate quality with an adverse effect of increasing the effect of the heat of hydration of the

cement. Due to this, it was found necessary to arrange a method of lowering the temperature of fresh concrete before placing. The study carried out on-site indicated that precooling the fresh concrete with chilled water-cooled using a containerised cooling plant using ammonia as a cooling agent to 5 °C and sprinkling the aggregate with water would suffice without additional measures of post-cooling. The average measured temperature of fresh concrete was 20°C.

The most critical thermal condition considered were the maximum curing temperature attained and maximum internal temperature differential which the specified maximum was temperature 20 °C.

The maximum temperature attained was measured using thermo-sensors positioned in the middle of the block. The maximum internal differential was determined as the difference between the maximum curing temperature and temperature at the surface of the block measured about one

centimetre from the concrete surface. The maximum internal and surface temperature measurements are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The maximum internal, surface temperature and computed internal differential temperature for mix 5

Figure 6: The concrete curing temperature for a lift of 2.5m, 330Kg/m³ of binder [mix 4].

6.0 MEASURES TO LOWER CONCRETE CURING TEMPERATURES

The following measures were taken to minimise the adverse effect of temperature rise within the mass concrete.

- 1) Minimum cement content was used to achieve the specified strength. The margin of structural concrete was set to

5 MPa while that of the massive dam concrete was set to 3 MPa.

- 2) Blended OPC and GGBS in the ratio of 1:1 were used for concrete production to lower the heat of hydration of cement.
- 3) The water-reducing agent was used to reduce the water demand and cement content to achieve the desired targeted compressive cube strength and workability.
- 4) The coarse aggregates were sprinkled with cold water so that some heat could be lost through evaporation.
- 5) Managing the construction procedure by fixing the formwork removal time to 5-7 days or more depending on the curing temperature of the concrete
- 6) The temperature was monitored using thermocouples in the inner part and the outer part so that the temperature gradient within the concrete mass could be determined.
- 7) Testing the massive concrete at 90 days instead of 28 days
- 8) The cement silo was painted with white reflective colour.

Figure 7: The adiabatic temperature for the sample of OPC and blend of OPC and GGBS

7.0 CONCRETE BATCHING, TRANSPORTATION AND PLACING

The batching of the concrete was carried out using three 2 m³ drum type mixers with a rated maximum output of 50 m³/hour. Immediately after mixing the concrete was

discharged into dump trucks and transported to a hopper feeding the 42 metres crane with conveyor belt mounted on a crane which was used to transport the fresh concrete. The concrete was transported and placed in a plastic state with slump ranging from 20-50 mm for massive dam concrete. For structural concrete, the slump ranged from 50-90 mm. The concrete vibration was carried out immediately after placing to ensure that the concrete compaction was completed before the concrete starts to stiffen.

Curing of concrete commenced before complete dry out to prevent surface cracks caused by early drying of concrete. This operation was done continuously using

water sprinkler, allowing the concrete to gain strength before being subjected to tensile stress caused by shrinkage and volume changes.

The concrete lift was left for a minimum of four days before concreting the next lift. This ensured that heat of hydration of the previous layer had been dissipated through the upper layer. The concreting time between two adjacent blocks was set a minimum of ten days.

The weather condition at the dam site was favourable, allowing the placement of concrete throughout the year. The weather data, as measured from the site weather station, is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Monthly climatic Condition - Dam Site*

	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
Mean Max.temperature(°C)	23	24	23	21	24	22	21	19	21	23	23	25
Mean Min. temperature(°C)	20	19	19	19	17	15	14	16	18	19	21	22
Ave. Temperature(°C)	22	21	21	20	19	17	16	18	19	21	22	23
Ave. Wind speed (m/s)	2	3	4	5	5	4	6	2	2	2	3	1

* Average for the period of 1998-99

8.0 FORMWORK

The formwork used for dam construction was quick-transfer climbing steel formwork. The forms for each lift were anchored on the step below with additional support provided with formwork ties. The formwork was left in place for at least five days before anchoring to the next lower lift so that the concrete strength was high enough to prevent pullout from the anchors.

The removal of formwork depended on the curing temperature of the concrete. Generally, the formwork was left in place for 5-7 days to reduce the possibility of having surface cracks caused by thermal shock.

9.0 CONCRETE TESTING

Several tests were specified in the contract documents. The testing was carried out using the relevant BS, AASHTO or ASTM

standards or following instructions given in the Technical specifications.

The permeability of concrete was tested in accordance with the instructions given in the project specifications whereby the concrete block having a dimension of 400x400x200 mm was subjected to a pressure of 2 bar for 14 days. The concrete was classified as impermeable when the measured water penetration depth was less than 100 mm.

10. SPECIFICATION AMENDMENTS

The following amendments were done to the Technical Specifications to suit site conditions:

- The structural concrete strength requirements were relaxed by 5 MPa.
- The age of testing for massive dam concrete was increased from 28 to 90 days because of the poor quality of the aggregates encountered within the project vicinity.
- The maximum aggregate size of massive dam concrete Mix 5 was reduced from 120 mm to 90 mm to

facilitate adequate transportation of the concrete using a conveyor belt.

- The slump of massive concrete was increased from 0 to 30 mm to facilitate the vibration of concrete using handheld poker vibrator.

11.0 CONCLUSION

Apart from the poor aggregate quality encountered within the project vicinity, the construction work of Lower Kihansi dam was carried out successfully. The concrete produced was generally of acceptable quality with aggregates embedded in a dense and durable matrix which will guarantee satisfactory performance of concrete.

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